

Solid Oxide Stack Development at Elcogen

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Elcogen solid oxide stacks are key enablers of the transition to a new energy scenario. This work provides an overview of the latest development activities at Elcogen. Throughout this manuscript, advancements on the stack level will be discussed with main focus on the flexibility and robustness of the elcoStack® in different operating modes. Such advancements are contextualized within the scaling up activities of the company, which will prepare Elcogen for the large scale deployment of solid oxide technology.

Introduction

Elcogen provides fuel cell and electrolysis unit cell, stack and stack module products for efficient clean power generation, green hydrogen and syngas production. Elcogen products are based on solid oxide cell technology designed to enable good performance, easy and robust manufacturing scale-up. To fit within this roadmap, Elcogen is building a manufacturing facility (Fig. 1) in Tallinn, Estonia which, once fully operational, will allow to manufacture of 240 MW worth of cells and 140 MW worth of stacks per year for green hydrogen production.

Figure 1. Pilot scale factory planned in Tallinn, Estonia

Elcogen's R&D efforts are dedicated to improve the performances of its product, starting from material science, component development and evaluations, validation and in depth characterization of stacks and integration of multiple stacks into modules for most

efficient system layouts. This paper will summarize the latest development activities at stack level for both fuel cell and electrolysis applications.

Elcogen stacks are built around the company's internally developed and manufactured unit cells. The unit cells are fuel electrode supported with cell structure combining fuel fuel electrode support and active layer (NiO/YSZ), electrolyte (YSZ), barrier layer (GDC), and oxygen electrode (LSC). The interconnect plates are manufactured from ferritic sheet metal and coated with oxide coating. The stack design for commercial application is called elcoStack® E3000 and the stack design for technology evaluation purposes elcoStack® E350. The difference between the design variants is the air supply means, i.e. elcoStack® E350 has fully manifolded air side structure as elcoStack® E3000 utilizes open air design.

Fig. 2 depicts the elcoStack® E350 (Fig. 2.a), the elcoStack® E3000 (Fig 2.b) and the 2x2 elcoModule® (Fig 2.c). The elcoStack® E350 shares the same flow distribution and electrical contacting structures as the elcoStack® E3000. This makes it a reliable platform where the detailed characterization can be performed at short stack level in controlled laboratory environment. The results obtained are still applicable to the elcoStack® E3000, which on the other hand is specifically designed for easy integration in multi-stack system. The shown elcoModule® enables efficient manifolding of four elcoStack E3000 for subsequent plant integration. Such module offers an easy-to-integrate interface to streamline the validation of prototype range systems. Similar concepts can then be upscaled to fit the need of larger systems.

Figure 2. a) elcoStack® E350 with 15 unit layers, fully manifolded air structure, all unit layers equipped with voltage measurement cables and in-stack thermocouple. b) elcoStack® E3000 with 119 unit layers and open air structure. c) 2x2 elcoModule® housing four pieces of elcoStack® E3000, including compression system, fuel and air connection points, current, voltage, temperature and pressure interfaces and housing slots.

Manufacturing Quality

Scaling up the manufacturing volumes is a crucial step to enable a large-scale deployment of Elcogen's solid oxide technology. While doing this, it is crucial to ensure that the quality of the manufactured products remain consistent with increased manufacturing throughput. Similarly, as the request for large scale system grows, it is paramount to make sure that every individual building block of such system behaves in a coherent way. Examples of such systems are developed in European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreements 101006667 (SO-FREE), 101069828 (FuelSOME), 101101439 (OUTFOX).

To facilitate the realization of such systems, Elcogen is monitoring the performance of every produced stack with quality assurance tests with as high detail level as is still practical without increasing the manufacturing costs. Quality assurance measurements are conducted according to IEC 62282-7-2.

Figure 3. Polarization curve showing statistical values gathered over one year of stacks manufactured at Elcogen

The current-voltage characteristics test results depicted in Fig. 3 highlight the reproducibility in the manufacturing process. The test is performed with H_2/N_2 with constant flow rate of 24.5 l_N/min of H_2 and 40 l_N/min of N_2 . Cathode side is fed with air at constant flow rate of 223 l_N/min . Inlet temperature for the air is 600 °C. Current is increased with 1 A/min sweep rate. The box plots represent 50% of the whole data collected on elcoStack® E3000 manufactured over one year. The whiskers represent the absolute maximum and minimum of the measured values. At open circuit voltage condition, the average value was 138.8 V, with minimum and maximum of 136.4 V and 140.3 V respectively. At 15 A point, the average value was 108.8, with minimum and maximum of 107.5 V and 110 V.

Robustness in temperature and load change

Extensive tests have been carried out to investigate the robustness of elcoStack® against temperature and load changes over a one-year period using as a platform the elcoStack® E350. The test consists of 66 cycles, each of them consisting of: i) heating up from cold (150°C) up to nominal operation temperature (600°C), ii) full performance tests where open circuit voltage (OCV) was recorded followed by a polarization curve up to nominal operation point (NOC - 30 A) and subsequent fuel utilization test (between 40% and 80%), iii) 100 h at NOC, iv) cool down from 600°C to 150°C. Heating and cooling rate was controlled to be equal to 120°C/h. The fuel used for the test was a 1/1 mixture of H₂/N₂ at 15,6 l_N/min (NOC condition). Fuel flow was stepwise decreased during the fuel utilization test while current was kept at a constant value of 30 A. Heating and cooling phases were performed using 5/95 mixture of H₂/N₂. Air feed was constant at 33 l_N/min throughout the test. A detailed view of one complete cycle is reported in Fig. 4. The different phases coded as light green for phases i) and iv), light yellow for phase ii) and light blue for phase iii).

Figure 4. Detailed view of one complete cycle

The chart shown in Fig 5. summarizes the test, showing the average voltage of the stack together with the temperature. The NOC condition is represented by the semi-continuous lines in the range of 900-850 mV, while the OCV measured after each thermocycle can be read in the range between 1190 – 1230 mV, with an average value of 1228 mV.

During this test, the degradation rate measured over the nominal operation segments was found to be 15 mOhm.cm²/kh or 0.4%/kh, thus equal to the steady state degradation tests performed in the past on the same stack platform^[1]. This test demonstrates that no

additional degradation is introduced through thermocycling, both from the NOC point and from the gas tightness of the stack, evaluated through the OCV.

Figure 5. Thermocycling experiment performed on elcoStack® E350

Fuel Cell Operation

Performance assessment has been performed on elcoStack® E3000 to further investigate its behavior in long term steady state operation and evaluate its robustness against thermal cycles. Test has been carried out in a controlled environment in a laboratory testbench capable of operating both with pure H₂ as well as natural gas. The test was scheduled to be concluded upon reaching one year of operation.

Long-term operation of the stack has been performed using natural gas as a fuel. Natural gas is mixed with steam feed prior to the reformer reactor. The steam-to-carbon ratio is 2.2. The gas composition fed to the stack is standardized in the test by controlling the outlet temperature of the steam reforming reactor to 590 °C. The resulting composition for the stack inlet is [CH₄] = 7%, [H₂O] = 26%, [CO] = 7%, [H₂] = 52%, [CO₂] = 8%. Fuel utilization in the test is 60% simulating conditions of a system equipped with anode exhaust gas recycle unit. The fuel cell cathode is fed with preheated air. The oxygen utilization is 22%. Both the air and fuel are heated to 590 °C for the stack inlet. The current at the nominal operation conditions is 30 A.

In Fig. 6, the stack power is reported over the whole duration of the test. Interruptions in the chart represent full thermocycles where the stack was cooled down to room temperature and heated up again. Degradation rate, calculated at the nominal operation point was linear with constant slope of 20 mOhm.cm²/1000h (i.e. 0.6%/1000h). No changes in performances were recorded after the stack has been thermocycled.

Figure 6. Long-term testing performed on the elcoStack® E3000 operated with reformed natural gas.

Electrolysis Operation

Elcogen stacks can be operated reversibly in fuel cell and electrolysis mode. As the interest in clean hydrogen production grows, solid oxide technology is rapidly emerging as a viable candidate to enable the transition to a sustainable energetic scenario. Elcogen stacks are part of several European Union as well as national funded projects under grant agreements 101101439 (OUTFOX), 838014 (C2FUEL), Business Finland funded project E-FUEL.

Fig. 7 represents a typical polarization curve of an elcoStack® E3000 under steam electrolysis operation. The chart shows the total stack voltage on left y-axis and the specific energy consumption by mass of produced hydrogen (SEC-m) on the right y-axis as a function of the input power. Each curve represents a different concentration of H₂ in the steam inlet stream, which offer a perspective on different possible scenarios of H₂ recycling in a real system.

The stack is operated at 680 °C with a fixed steam supply of 4 kg/h and an H₂ supply between 9 l_N/min and 90 l_N/min, depending on the measurement condition. Air supply was kept constant at 330 l_N/min. The stack SEC was measured to be 33.3 kWh/kg at 10 kW input power range.

Figure 7. Polarization curve measured on elcoStack® E3000 operated in steam electrolysis mode with different H₂ concentration, ranging from 10% to 52%.

Scaling Up – New generation elcoStack® E3000

The next generation of the elcoStack® E3000, shown in Fig. 8.a, has been designed to address several fundamental aspects of the stack, from the manufacturing up to the actual performances. From the manufacturing point of view, the stack has been designed to enable significant cost reduction compared to the current generation. This will enable, once full-scale production has been reached, to make solid oxide technology more affordable with positive impact on its uptake from the markets point of view. Such achievement has been also made possible through reduction of the number of parts employed, focusing also on reducing the use of raw materials. At the same time, lower amounts of components per stack entails a reduced number of interfaces which conversely lead to an increase in robustness and reduced failure probability. Special attention has also been paid to ensuring that the fuel distribution characteristics were improved, thus enabling to extend the range of operation when it comes to single pass fuel utilization, as shown in Fig. 8.b where the performances of the next generation stack are compared to the current elcoStack® E3000. For both stacks, the test was performed at part load (15A) to highlight possible differences in fuel utilization dependency and by using a 1/1 ratio of H₂/N₂, fuel flow rate was decreased stepwise to achieve the desired fuel utilization. Stabilization time at each flow rate level is 2 min. Cathode side was fed with air at constant flow rate of 327 l_N/min. The inlet temperature of the air was 590 °C and for the fuel 585 °C.

Figure 8. a) new generation elcoStack® E3000 and b) comparison of its fuel utilization characteristics compared to the current generation.

Summary

Elcogen development activities aim at pushing the boundaries of efficiency, robustness, and cost competitiveness of solid oxide stacks for a broad range of applications, from clean power generation to green hydrogen production. The lower operating temperature of Elcogen stacks enables significant cost reduction thanks to the ease of selecting industrially available materials and easily scalable manufacturing processes. This work offers an overview on the ongoing activities at Elcogen in developing its product for mass manufacturing and for a broad spectrum of applications.

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References

1. M. Noponen, P. Torri, J. Göös, J. Puranen, T. Lehtinen, S. Pylypko and E. Öunpuu. ECS Trans. **103** (1), 267-274 (2021).